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Lived Experiences of MAPEH V Parents on Modular Learning: Challenges, Strategies, and Insights

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Abstract

This phenomenological study aimed to determine parents' struggles, coping mechanisms, and insights in assisting their children using MAPEH modules. With modular learning, parents encountered technological, economical, and instructional difficulties. Due to restricted educational opportunities, unstable economic conditions, and family obligations, low-income parents have additional challenges in this changing educational environment. Additionally, the lack of sufficient educational resources, such as learning tools, further compounds these difficulties. As a result, these parents are often left at a disadvantage, struggling to adapt to the evolving educational system in a home-based learning support. Further, this study utilized a phenomenology approach and a purposive sampling technique; the (10) participants were parents of Grade 5 MAPEH students in Guinuyoran, Valencia City, who were identified for in-depth interviews and observation. Thematic analysis was used as a data analysis tool to interpret the data gathered. The results revealed that parents experienced everyday struggles such as time management concerns, limited knowledge of the MAPEH subject, doubts about their learning outcomes, and limited patience with their children's attitudes. To cope with these difficulties, the parents decided to find meaningful strategies such as seeking help from the teacher and family members, employing reward systems, relying on the Internet, and creating a supportive environment. Moreover, parents also shared various insights regarding modular learning, such as not effective for their children, disadvantaged to economically deprived families, and added baggage for intellectually challenged parents. In conclusion, since education is lifelong learning, educators, administrators, and stakeholders should work together to develop comprehensive instruction to obtain quality education despite the changes in the mode of instruction.

Keywords: *modules, struggles, strategies, insights, phenomenology*

Introduction

Parents faced instructional, financial, and technical challenges with modular learning (Ogurlu et al., 2020). Specifically, parents with lower education levels may need more knowledge to effectively assist their children's development (Azubuike & Aina, 2020). Parents from low-income backgrounds confront heightened obstacles in this evolving educational landscape, compounded by limited access to education, economic instability, and familial responsibilities (Idulog et al., 2022). Amidst this global backdrop, the Philippines stands at the forefront of educational reform, facing the challenges posed by the transition to modular learning. As nations strive to bridge the digital divide and ensure inclusive education for all, understanding the experiences of Grade 5 MAPEH parents within this local context is paramount.

Accordingly, the importance of increased parental involvement in modular learning cannot be neglected (Suico et al., 2022). Recognizing parents as essential facilitators and para-teachers in the educational journey, their active engagement is critical in enhancing learners' participation and academic achievement. Collaborative efforts among parents, educators, and administrators foster an environment conducive to tailored teaching approaches and curriculum adjustments, ensuring the unique needs of each learner are met effectively within the modular learning framework. This present study was of great importance as it not only talked about the experiences of the parents but also accounted for their coping strategies and insights while facing the struggles brought by modular learning of their Grade 5 children while studying MAPEH subjects.

Interestingly, this study was anchored to several essential models and theories. Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler's model confirms a link between parental role and self-efficacy (Afolabi, 2014). The use of Hoover-Dempsey & Sandler's model explains variations in parental responses, examines how parental motivations impact their efforts in assisting with Grade 5 MAPEH modules, considers expectations, perceived value, and outcomes, investigates the role of school invitations and support mechanisms in influencing parental struggles.

Fascinatingly, this present study held great significance not only to educational institutions but also to different branches of society. This study aligned with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal 4, which focuses on Quality Education. The goal aims to achieve affordable, equal, and inclusive access to quality education, emphasizing attaining higher education standards despite diverse backgrounds (United Nations, 2023). In this context, the research can serve as a valuable reference for global researchers exploring related topics, including the challenges, experiences, strategies, and insights related to parents assisting their children with modular learning modules.

Moreover, considering the Department of Education's (2023) goal to strengthen the Homeschooling Program for Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM), as outlined in DepEd Order No. 001, series of 2022, this study provides a platform for parents to express their concerns. The insights gathered can contribute valuable knowledge to various sectors, particularly the education department and other stakeholders. By examining the struggles faced by parents, the public agency can formulate a framework to address these challenges effectively. For the education sector, the study offers information on potential programs or alternatives to meet the needs of parents. It

also guides education program specialists in developing or refining specific programs and curricula to alleviate parental struggles during modular learning.

Research Questions

This study aimed to discover the lived experiences of MAPEH parents in modular learning. The specific objectives are to find out the struggles and experiences of MAPEH parents in assisting their children during modular learning, to determine the coping mechanisms and strategies of the MAPEH parents on the problems or struggles they encountered, and to know the insights of parents about modular learning. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the struggles and experiences of MAPEH V parents in assisting their children during modular learning?
2. What are the coping mechanisms and strategies of the MAPEH V Parents on the problems or struggles they encountered?
3. What are the insights of the MAPEH V Parents about modular learning?

Literature Review

Several studies have been conducted on parents' experiences during modular learning. According to the Department of Education (2022b), in the Philippines, Modular Distance Learning is the predominant method, preferred by 75.1% of kindergarten to Grade 12 learners across all sectors, totaling 20,688,555 students. This personalized approach utilizes Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) in print or digital format based on learner needs, addressing challenges like limited internet access and the absence of required devices. Public schools and State Universities/Colleges (SUCs/LUCs) overwhelmingly favor MDL (Print) at 82.0% and 39.3%, respectively. Overall, MDL remains the top choice, influenced by public sector preferences, while some regions also adopt Blended Learning and Open Distance Learning (ODL).

Parents face significant challenges in balancing caregiving and educational roles, impacting their ability to assist children with education (Paco et al., 2021). The struggle involves managing various obligations, maintaining learner motivation, ensuring accessibility, and achieving learning outcomes, further intensifying parents' economic, psychological, and social burdens during distance learning (Ogurlu et al., 2020; Lase et al., 2020). Limited time, the inability to assume teaching roles, and conflicts with time management exacerbate parental challenges (Lardizabal-Dado, 2020; Olivo, 2021). These challenges include managing multiple obligations, maintaining learner motivation, and achieving learning outcomes. Limited time and conflicts with teaching roles exacerbate parental struggles.

Additionally, challenges persist in parents' engagement with Modular Distance Learning (MDL), with some needing more knowledge to facilitate their children's education (Kintanar et al., 2021). Parents with limited education find it challenging to provide necessary assistance, hindering adequate support due to inadequate knowledge of specific topics and time constraints for other household priorities (Olivo, 2021). This lack of knowledge on specific topics and time constraints from other household priorities further exacerbates the difficulties parents encounter in facilitating their children's learning.

Furthermore, the study by Salvador and Sacay (2023) underscores the mediating role of parents' confidence in connecting psychological distress and regulatory emotional efficacy to children's emotional regulation and negativity. The desire for independence among students poses another challenge, as parents, acting as facilitators, often find themselves doing the modules, hindering children's self-reliance development (Abucejo et al., 2022). These findings suggest a delicate balance that parents must strike between providing support and fostering independence in their children during the learning process.

Also, the study by Gumapac et al. (2021) noted the impact of increased social media use on children's engagement, leading to distraction, compliance-focused learning, and hindering the development of self-reliance. The study indicates that prolonged exposure to social media may impede the development of self-reliance among students, as they become accustomed to external stimuli and guidance rather than cultivating independent learning skills.

On the other hand, parents or guardians have a pivotal role in acquiring essential learning materials through collaboration with teachers, barangay representatives, and stakeholders (Gumapac et al., 2021). This responsibility involves communication with teachers and community officials, as Manlangit et al. (2020) highlighted. Actively involved in school communication, progress monitoring, and seeking guidance from peers, parents play a significant role in supporting their child's education (Gumapac et al., 2021). These studies emphasize the crucial role of parents in obtaining necessary learning materials through collaboration with educators and community stakeholders, underscoring the importance of effective communication channels. Additionally, they highlight parents' active engagement in school communication, progress monitoring, and seeking guidance from peers, emphasizing their significant contribution to supporting their child's educational journey.

In modular learning, parents serve as home facilitators and motivators, providing compliments, encouragement, and rewards to enhance their child's motivation (Gumapac et al., 2021). Parents actively engage in encouraging positive opinions and feelings toward education, utilizing positive verbal reinforcement for motivation (Gumapac et al., 2021), aligning with the recommendation of Manlangit et al. (2020) to offer praise, encouragement, and rewards for enhanced learning motivation. The studies highlight the crucial role of parents as facilitators and motivators in modular learning, emphasizing their use of positive verbal reinforcement, compliments, and rewards

to enhance their child's motivation.

Besides, UNESCO Beirut (2020) recommended maintaining open communication channels, engaging with teachers and peers, and employing diverse learning methods for optimal educational outcomes. By engaging in diverse learning methods and fostering collaborative relationships, stakeholders can create an environment conducive to optimal learning outcomes. Additionally, this intentional response underscored the acknowledgment of the learning environment's crucial impact in shaping their children's educational journey (UNESCO Beirut, 2020). This highlights the recognition of the significant influence of the learning environment on children's educational development, emphasizing the importance of creating supportive and conducive learning environments to facilitate positive learning outcomes.

On the other side, Bayucca (2021) highlights the challenge of children struggling to concentrate on their studies at home due to additional responsibilities. Functionally illiterate parents may have difficulty teaching their children, impacting modular distance learning (Anzaldo, 2021). A significant decrease in learners' academic performance during MDL implementation suggests that the method may not be effective for some children (Dargo & Dimas, 2021). Parents with lower education levels may need more knowledge to effectively assist their children's development (Azubuike & Aina, 2020). Parents' educational limitations may hinder their ability to effectively support their children's learning, potentially contributing to a decline in academic performance. These findings underscore the importance of targeted support mechanisms to address the diverse needs of both students and parents in the context of modular learning.

Also, studies underscore the profound impact of challenges faced by parents, intensifying economic burdens. These challenges disproportionately affect financially struggling families (Ogurlu et al., 2020; Lase et al., 2020). This underscores the likelihood that financially struggling families bear a disproportionate share of these challenges, potentially widening existing socioeconomic disparities in educational outcomes. Likewise, Ogurlu et al. (2020) emphasize the need for targeted interventions to support intellectually challenged families navigating the educational journey. Tailored interventions are necessary to aid intellectually challenged families in navigating the complexities of the educational journey. By addressing the unique needs of these families, such targeted interventions can mitigate the challenges they face and promote equitable access to educational opportunities.

Methodology

Participants

The participants were selected explicitly from Guinuyoran, Valencia City, and Bukidnon. Ten parents wherein five (5) males and five (5) females were purposely chosen as the respondents. It is sufficient to capture diverse perspectives, enriching research findings or data saturation (Deakin University, 2019; Campbell, 2015; Baškarada, 2014). Sarfo et al. (2021) mentioned that ten participants are enough saturated data in a phenomenological study and a smaller sample size is adequate for phenomenological studies to enable recognize the underlying logic of human experiences and the ability to communicate accurately.

In this study, purposive random sampling was applied in qualitative investigation to gain insights into the various struggles and experiences of Grade 5 MAPEH parents during modular learning. Purposive sampling is a random sampling methodology where the sample group is targeted to have specific attributes. This method can be used in many populations but is more effective with a smaller sample size and a more homogenous population (Singh & Jadhav, 2023).

Moreover, participants in this study were carefully selected based on specific inclusion criteria. Eligible individuals were parents from Guinoyoran, Valencia City, and Bukidnon whose children were currently engaged in modular learning. They needed relevant and direct experiences regarding the struggles encountered during this learning modality.

Additionally, participants were required to be 18 years of age or older and to demonstrate a willingness to participate in in-depth interviews and observations. The study aimed to include a diverse group of parents, encompassing various social statuses such as married, solo parents, or separated individuals, as well as differing socioeconomic backgrounds—low, middle, or high. Both male and female participants with one or more children, regardless of their employment status or educational attainment, were considered for inclusion.

Conversely, specific criteria were established for exclusion from the study. Parents residing outside the specified locale were not eligible, nor were those who enrolled their children in public or private schools utilizing blended or online learning methods. Additionally, individuals unwilling to participate in interviews and observations were excluded. Lastly, parents aged 17 years and younger were not considered for the study, ensuring that all participants met the minimum age requirement for informed consent.

Parents who have firsthand experience of struggles and experiences during modular learning are included in this study (Biñas & Garvida, 2023). Moreover, suppose a qualified participant wants to withdraw from the study or refuses to answer at least two (2) research questions. In that case, he/she will be automatically withdrawn as a participant in the study. Additionally, they mentioned that participant withdrawal is frequent in qualitative research for diverse reasons. The researcher must acknowledge and respect participants' decisions, maintaining confidentiality and privacy. Documenting withdrawals is crucial for transparency, and understanding reasons can guide improvements in future studies.

Instrument

The instrument used in this study was a researcher-made tool designed to gather comprehensive insights through in-depth interviews and observation. In-depth interviews consist of three primary research questions, supplemented by 11 guide questions and ten probing questions, while observation used an event sampling record sheet. This structured approach allows in-depth exploration of participants' experiences and perspectives regarding the modular learning system.

The instrument was developed by the researcher, who created the interview guide questions and observation tool. Esteemed individuals, including four internal validators from the University of Mindanao and one external validator, critically reviewed the instrument to ensure its validation, rigor, and relevance. After the rigorous validation of esteemed validators using the Validation Sheet for Research Questionnaire in Qualitative Study from the University of Mindanao Professional Schools, the instrument achieved an impressive average validation rating of 90, indicating a high level of agreement among validators on its appropriateness and effectiveness for the study's objectives.

Procedure

This present qualitative study used phenomenological design. Qualitative research is valuable for uncovering feelings, beliefs, and motivating behaviors through questions about how, what, and why. It relies on inductive reasoning, extracting broad themes from individual experiences to generate hypotheses (Bazen et al., 2021). Phenomenology is like delving into the deeper meanings of everyday experiences or zooming in on specific aspects. It is all about trying to see things from someone else's point of view. Think of it as stepping into someone's shoes to understand why they do what they do based on how they see the world (Tenny et al., 2022). Moreover, this research chose phenomenology as it aligns well with the academic pursuit at hand. The study solely seeks to capture the firsthand experiences, coping mechanisms, and perspectives of parent participants who have faced difficulties during modular distance learning. Thus, it was evident that a phenomenological approach is appropriate for the research context.

On the other hand, thematic analysis, grounded in the Collaizi method, is a valuable qualitative data analysis method. The process involves familiarizing, coding, identifying, reviewing, defining, and labeling themes and writing comprehensive findings to inform future studies (Wa-Mbaleka and Rosario, (2022). This method involves gathering rich, qualitative data through structured interviews and observations (Wirahana et al., 2018), which aligns well with exploring the challenges parents face navigating the modular learning system in the context of Grade 5 MAPEH education. By employing the Collaizi Method, one can systematically analyze the experiences and perspectives of parents, uncovering the multifaceted issues encountered in this specific educational setting. This approach allows for a comprehensive examination of the complexities surrounding modular learning, shedding light on parents' various struggles as they support their children's education in the MAPEH subject area.

During the thematic analysis, the researcher assigned codes that stand as the pseudonyms of the participants for easy classification. Also, this was to imply anonymity among participants—consequently, the codes for each participant. Specifically, this study used inductive coding during the thematic analysis. Inductive coding is well-suited for phenomenological research as it allows researchers to derive codes directly from the data, aligning with the focus on understanding participants' lived experiences without preconceptions. In a phenomenological study, researchers typically identify meaningful themes from interview transcripts through an iterative process of constant comparison, capturing the complexities of the phenomenon. This flexible approach ensured that the researcher stayed close to participants' perspectives, facilitating the discovery of unanticipated insights and a rich understanding of the lived experience (Bihu, 2023).

To develop this study, the researcher diligently worked towards fulfilling trustworthiness requirements, including credibility, reliability, confirmability, and transferability, as Shenton (2004) outlined. Ethical considerations were paramount, ensuring anonymity and safeguarding of respondents' identities. Maintaining privacy and confidentiality was fundamental throughout the research process.

In this study, trustworthiness was paramount, guiding the researcher in their multifaceted approach to data collection; by taking on various roles—observer, transcriber, translator, analyst, and encoder—the researcher aimed to preserve the authenticity of participant responses. Credibility was established through in-depth interviews and observations, focusing on participants' experiences and native languages (Korstjens and Moser, 2018). This attention to detail allowed for an authentic interpretation of their perspectives, reinforcing the integrity of the research.

The study also emphasized transferability, ensuring findings could resonate beyond the immediate context. Comprehensive documentation and background information were provided, enhancing transparency (Lincoln & Guba, 1992). Additionally, dependability was achieved through overlapping methodologies, which allowed for data saturation and consistent findings. An audit trail was maintained to bolster confirmability, enabling other researchers to verify the results. By focusing on these aspects of trustworthiness, the study ensured reliable outcomes and offered valuable insights into the challenges and strategies parents face in modular learning environments.

This study strictly adheres to ethical protocols set by the University of Mindanao Ethics and Research Committee. The researcher obtained parental permission, ensured appropriate recruiting, assessed and mitigated risks, and obtained authorization and consent from the study sample. Participants were assured of data protection and voluntary participation. Informed consent was obtained from parents

after discussing the research purpose. Ethical measures were observed in all study phases.

Results and Discussion

In this section, the results of the study are presented and discussed with reference. It also delved into the rich and multifaceted insights that emerged from the qualitative investigation, providing understanding of the struggles and perspectives of MAPEH parents during modular learning related to the research questions. Through thematic analysis from in-depth interviews and observation captured the diverse narratives and viewpoints of the participants.

Furthermore, table 1 presented the themes extracted from the responses of participants regarding their experiences and challenges in assisting their children with Grade 5 MAPEH modular distance learning. There is a total of four themes—time management concerns, limited knowledge and resources in MAPEH 5 subjects, doubts towards achieving learning outcomes, and limited patience towards child's attitude. Additionally, it elucidated the key concepts or core ideas that define the scope of these themes, providing a comprehensive understanding of the parents' perspectives and difficulties.

Table 1. Lived experiences of Grade 5 Parents on MAPEH Modular Learning

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Subthemes</i>
Time Management Concerns	Limited Time Resources
Limited Knowledge and Resources in MAPEH 5 Subject	Conflict with Other Responsibilities
	Difficulty Understanding the Topic
Doubts towards Achieving Learning Outcomes	Lack of Knowledge
	Limited Monitoring of Children's Learning
Limited Patience towards Child's Attitude	Insufficient Knowledge and Doubts Regarding Actual Learning
	Inadequate Patience for Teaching
	Exhaustion as a Limiting Factor
	Excuses and Distractions

As to the first theme, Time Management Concerns, participants from the in-depth interview have the same sentiments as they shared that teaching and helping their children in their module took much time. The parents shared that it added to the things that they must do. Specifically, for mothers, they said that aside from being bombarded with house chores, they needed to insert in their time routine the module checking and monitoring of their children. They consider this a struggle since they are not used to it in the normal set-up. Participants shared:

“Kuan siya ang bata bitaw, oh kanang kapoy siya kay dili sila mag balansi sa oras ug ayha na sila submit day before sa ting pasa kanang ga cram sila maong malagot ko” (IDI P1)

“I find it tiresome because they can hardly manage their time. It's a reason that causes them to submit school requirements late. Generally, it crammed them at most times, and it seriously angers me.”

“Oh kanang naa siyay negative effect as a parent kay kanang imong time usahay maadto sa bata.” (IDI P3)

“I totally agree that it has negative effects as a parent because you have no choice but to give almost all of your time to your kids.”

“Grabe gyud kahago kay labina ipasahay na ang module wa pay answer di kami nalang mag answer.” (IDI P8)

“It was very tiresome especially when deadlines are fast approaching.”

Observations:

The mother left the child who was doing the module for a moment because she was making milk for the baby. You can see the mother struggling in assisting the child because there's a baby. (OF2)

In the subject or even in handling his child, one can see how the father was struggling. His other child also got jealous and wanted him to assist him/her as well. (OM5)

In terms of time management, as one of the struggles of parents assisting Grade 5 MAPEH modules, the findings resonate with theoretical frameworks such as Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler's model of parental self-efficacy and Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory (Afolabi, 2014; Bronfenbrenner, 1979). This is congruent to the idea of parental beliefs and specific involvement forms impacting children's learning outcomes, emphasizing the need for interventions to enhance parental efficacy and create supportive environments conducive to involvement.

In connection too this, there is a congruent study by Paco et al. (2021) and Lardizabal-Dado (2020) that highlights the economic, psychological, and social burdens faced by parents, suggesting strategies such as flexible scheduling and community-based support programs. Integrating theoretical frameworks with empirical evidence enables educators and policymakers to develop comprehensive interventions addressing parental struggles and promoting positive learning outcomes for Grade 5 MAPEH students in modular learning settings.

On the other hand, the second theme emphasized their struggles about the Limited Knowledge and Resources in MAPEH subject. The participants expressed the same sentiments that they have only limited knowledge and resources in the MAPEH subject. The participants admitted that upon assisting their children they are having a hard time because they are not familiar, capable, or knowledgeable to teach their children, especially the MAPEH subject. And it is challenging for them to support the learning needs of their children. While some of the parents were literate enough to be as functional as they would be to the community, it does not mean they are already qualified to teach their children in terms of academics. Participants shared also that they have limited access to learning materials and resources to assist their children efficiently and effectively. Participants shared:

“Naglisod ko labina anang mga notes kailangan pa jud mangudigo, bisan pa ug kanang parents ko nakaagi man gyud ko ana pero lisod jud siya hinumdoman kinahanaglan pa jud mag research mag kinahanglan pako ug internet para maka search ta kung unsa to na notes kay wala may libro” (IDI P4)

“It was difficult especially the parts that tackle about music notes because it was really hard to remember. Even though I am a parent, I find the topic so difficult; what more for my kid at her age? Considering the fact that there were no books provided, we needed to research on the Internet so would understand well.”

“Naa wa jud koy hanaw aning health oyyy di kayo nako ma pa tudlo sa ilaha labina ng mga kalahian sa lawas. Maglisod ko ug explain sa ilaha. (IDI P5)

“I really am not knowledgeable about Health so I don’t teach them anything about it. Most especially about the parts of the body, I really don’t know how to explain it so I just let them understand on their own.”

“Akong struggle is katong mga lessons na wala naagii sukad sa mga ginikanan daghan kaayo didto na di gyud ko kasabot” (IDI P8)

“One of the struggles I encountered was with the lessons that we were not familiar about.”

Observations:

She cannot express well what the notes mean. (OF1)

It was obvious that the mother has a little knowledge of the subject but cannot really explain well. (OF2)

Additionally, in assisting their child's Grade 5 MAPEH module, parents' limited knowledge and resources pose significant challenges. These struggles align with Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory, highlighting the influence of broader social and cultural factors on parental involvement (Bronfenbrenner, 1979).

Furthermore, challenges persist in parents' engagement with Modular Distance Learning (MDL), with some lacking the knowledge to facilitate their children's education (Kintanar et al., 2021). This was true with the situation of Grade 5 parents during MAPEH modular distance learning who lacked basic knowledge and strategic method in teaching. With this, imparting knowledge to their children became a heavy burden. Notably, almost all of the parent participants were struggling with MAPEH subject like difficulty in reading musical notes, struggles in demonstrating certain dance step or exercise, has trouble interpreting or appreciating certain art or simply reading and understanding the mode of language which is English. Many parents opted to use open browser and technology, but these were not enough to explicitly teach their children when at the first they themselves were struggling to learn this subject.

Subsequently, this is supported to the study of Olivo (2021) further underscored the dilemma, as parents with limited education found themselves challenged to provide necessary assistance due to inadequate knowledge on certain topics and time constraints for household priorities. The findings resonate with previous studies, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to address parental challenges in modular learning environments.

Third was the Doubts towards Achieving the Learning Outcomes of the students. Modular learning can be less transparent compared to the face-to-face classroom setting. Participants agreed that they have a lot of doubts about achieving the learning outcomes of their students. Especially in the MAPEH subject that requires performance tasks, the participants admitted that they were not sure if tasks were correct. Participants shared that their worries are their child's academic development and progress. It was a challenge to them to make their children stay focused and motivated in their module. Participants shared:

“Di gyud nato ma monitor if nakatoun ba ang atong mga bata” (IDI P1)

“We cannot monitor our children if they have learned anything.”

“Malipay biya mi na module lang ang among anak kay di kayo gasto ug balon, snack, ug gamit sa eskwelahan pero usahay mabalaka sad ta ug nakatoun ba or wala” (IDI P4)

“We feel happy that our children are now in a modular setting because there are fewer expenses, snacks, and school supplies but we worry about whether they have actually learned or not.”

“Sa akona wala kaayo makatudlo mao ng mabalaka ta no ug makasabot ba siya ana nga mga module labina sa MAPEH kay wala biya kaayo nag assist sa iyaha unya murag ga self-learning ra ang mga bata.” (IDI P9)

“In my case, no one can teach that much, which is why we got worried if s/he understands those modules, especially in MAPEH, where there’s no one who assists him/her, then it seems like the children are only self-learning.”

Observations:

The child just listened, but you can see that the child did not understand because s/he doesn’t answer when asked. (OF1)

The child did not follow because the mother’s explanation was lacking. (OF2)

The child acted angry and cried because he did not want to do the modules. (OF4)

Moreover, in terms of doubts of parents towards achieving learning outcomes, as one of the struggles of parents, this affirms the theory of Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler (Afolabi, 2014), which emphasizes the pivotal role of parental involvement in educational settings. The doubts expressed by parents regarding their children’s progress in Grade 5 MAPEH modules reflect concerns about their efficacy in assisting with their child’s learning, as outlined in the five-level analysis proposed by Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler. These doubts underscore the importance of parental belief systems, specific involvement forms, mechanisms, mediating variables, and student outcomes (Walker et al., 2005).

As this theme unfolded, revealing a subtle yet pervasive undercurrent of uncertainty. While the understanding cast parents in the role of essential contributors and guides, the study by Salvador and Sacay (2023) brought to light the intricate emotional and psychological challenges veiled beneath the surface. Doubts about the effectiveness of Modular Learning methodologies and uncertainties regarding their ability to provide adequate support became intense hurdles, painting a comprehensive picture of the emotional toll on parents.

As for the fourth theme, Limited Patience towards a Child’s Attitude, the participants from the in-depth interviews, and observations shared common experiences and struggles about their child’s behavior towards modular learning. Authority has been one of the struggles of parents in giving instructions in their child’s module. They considered this as a struggle because children were not focused and did not follow the instruction they gave to accomplish their module. Participants also shared that they only have a little patience because of their limited time and having other responsibilities such as household chores and work. Participants shared:

“Isip usa ka papa, akong obserbaran pud is ang mga kinaiya sa atong mga bata. Nakita nako sa akong anak nga kung ga module murag wala lang sa iyaha, answer answer lang di gyud siya maningkamot, kanang muingon ko nga mag answer na sa module wala lang gyud sa iyaha.” (IDI P2)

“As a father, one thing I’ve noticed is our children’s attitude toward modules; whenever I watch my child doing modules, it appears to be nothing for them, and when I tell it was time to answer your modules, s/he just does it with no effort”

“Kalisod kay nalahi man ang set up sa mga bata mag basa ra man sila ug answer sa module unya akong bata di gyud hilig ug basa mag pasumangil dayon na sakit sakit mao ng maglagot ka.” (IDI P3)

“Struggle, due to the change in the set-up; they will just read and answer to their modules, but my child doesn’t like to read, then will have a lot of excuses that make me upset.”

“Kana mag tudlo ka nga daghan kaayo ug pasumangil ang bata di gyud mo makahuman kay daghan ug arte.” (IDI P7)

“They also make several excuses everytime I teach them, which contributes to the delay.”

Observations:

The mother asked the child to repeat but the child did not listen and became silly. (OF1)

The mother was already annoyed because the child was no longer focusing. (OF2)

She asked the child to read, but the child did not obey and was silly. Mother was starting to get angry. (OF3)

Interestingly, the result of limited patience towards a child’s attitude aligns with Sociocultural Theory (Vygotsky, 1978), which emphasizes the impact of social and cultural factors on learning. Parents, as facilitators, play a crucial role in fostering independent learning while providing support. Challenges faced by parents in maintaining patience and engaging their children during modular learning. The theory emphasizes on guided learning underscores the importance of effective communication patterns within the family context.

In addition to this, in the intricate landscape of Grade 5 MAPEH parents navigating Modular Learning, parents grappled with the technicalities of modular learning. Their patience wore thin in response to evolving attitudes, creating emotional strain. Whether facing technological hurdles or shifts in learning attitudes, this theme revealed the delicate balance required for a positive learning environment. Moreover, the study by Gumapac et al. (2021) noted the impact of increased social media use on children’s engagement, leading to distraction, compliance-focused learning, and hindering the development of self-reliance.

Conversely, Table 2 delineated the themes related to the coping mechanisms employed by Grade 5 parents in response to the challenges posed by modular learning these are—seeking guidance from the teachers and family, employing rewards system, integrating

technology and online resources, and creating a supportive environment. It further expounded on the core strategies and techniques that parents utilized to overcome these obstacles.

Table 2. *Coping Mechanisms of Grade 5 Parents in difficulties brought by MAPEH modular learning*

Themes	Subthemes
Seeking Guidance from the Teachers and Family	Teacher Consultation through Technology Community Support from Neighbors and Broadening Support Network
Employing Reward System	Consistent motivation through Rewards Financial and Non-Financial Incentives
Integrating Technology and Online Resources	Internet Browsing for Learning Diverse Online Sources and technology as a learning tool
Creating a Supportive Learning Environment	Collective Understanding and Support Coping Strategies through Assistance Collaboration between Parent

As for the first theme, Seeking Guidance from Teachers and Family, the participants shared this as a strategy to cope with the struggles they encounter because this was one of the easiest ways to accomplish the modules. It was also evident to the parents that reaching out through social media or calling the teachers of their child has been a coping act by the parents whenever they have clarifications or questions about the module. Family members also played an important role in coping with those struggles. Participants shared that knowledgeable family members were a big help to them, especially those contents that they are not familiar with. Participants shared:

“Pina ag isa Google, mangutana sa maestra or manawag kay nay number or thru messenger.” (IDI P6)

“By using Google, ask the teacher through a phone call or messenger app.”

“Mao ng ang module masolbad ang uban dili gyud ug usahay kani sang mga silingan makatabang pud ni usahay kay pare pareha ra man mi.” (IDI P9)

“Also, some neighbors can also lend a hand because we have a sort of similar situation.”

“Usahay ug di ko maka assist akong mga pag umangkon or isgoon nako na gradahon akong ipa adto didto ang mga bata.” (IDI P8)

“Sometimes, if I can’t assist, I tell my nieces, nephews, or siblings who have knowledge about it to go and help my kids.”

Observation:

The mother doesn’t have enough knowledge in Health; that’s why she said the child’s older sibling will be the one to teach it. (OM3)

The result, seeking guidance from teachers and family, as one of the strategies of parents coping with the struggles encountered in modular learning, affirms the theoretical perspectives of Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler’s model. According to Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler’s model, parental involvement is influenced by various factors, including parental belief systems, specific involvement forms, mechanisms, mediating variables, and student outcomes (Walker et al., 2005).

Furthermore, in the context of the coping strategy observed in seeking guidance from teachers and family, parents are actively engaging with the educational system and seeking assistance to overcome challenges, demonstrating a level of involvement consistent with the model’s framework. By reaching out to teachers through technology and consulting knowledgeable family members and neighbors, parents are aligning their actions with the model’s emphasis on parental motivations impacting efforts in assisting with learning modules (Gumapac et al., 2021). This illustrates how parental beliefs and motivations influence their engagement with their children’s education, particularly in navigating the complexities of modular learning.

On the other hand, the second theme was Employing a Reward System. This coping strategy shared by parents was an effective strategy to motivate their children to answer their module. By offering rewards or money parents can encourage their children to participate in their module session to stay engaged and focused. It was also a way to achieve learning goals or complete the modules of their children. This strategy was to foster intrinsic motivation while providing external encouragement. Participants shared:

“Sa akosa sir naa gyud kay reward kay usahay mas ma motivate man ang bata kung naa kay ibaylo sa ilaha panangitan kanang muana ko tagaan tika ug snack answeri imong module pero usahay ug wala kwarta ikahtag na di gyud ma answeran ang module.” (IDI P4)

“For me, sir, you should have a reward because sometimes the children get motivated to do their modules if you have something to give in return. For example, I’ll say, ‘I will give you a snack if you’ll answer your modules.’ But sometimes, when you have no money to give, they will not answer their modules.”

“Magastoon nalang gyud pud ta kay atoa nalang man ug tagaan ug kwarta para naa lay ma answer o di ba kaha snack para lang gyud maansweran ang module.” (IDI P10)

“I’ve got to spend money and give him/her some or maybe a snack just for him/her to answer the module.”

“Usahay tagaan sad nato ug pahalipay mao ng makagasto jud ka.” (IDI P10)

“I often give them rewards so they’d be motivated to do more.”

Observation:

The father told him that he would give him money. (OM4)

Consequently, the result employing a reward system, as one of the strategies of parents in coping with difficulties encountered in modular learning, affirmed the theory of sociocultural theory. Drawing upon Sociocultural Theory, which emphasizes the role of social interactions and cultural tools in learning, the implementation of a reward system reflects the social dynamic between parents and children (Vygotsky, 1978). By offering rewards or incentives, parents not only provide external encouragement but also scaffold their children's learning experiences, guiding them towards achieving learning goals within the modular learning context. This aligns with concept of guided learning, where adults or peers provide support to facilitate a child's understanding and mastery of tasks.

Additionally, studies have indicated the effectiveness of employing rewards such as praise, encouragement, and rewards as a coping strategy for parents in modular learning contexts (Gumapac et al., 2021; Manlangit et al., 2020). These findings support the notion that employing a reward system is an effective strategy for parents to cope with challenges in modular learning, aligning with theoretical frameworks of cognitive development and sociocultural theory. Understanding the role of rewards in motivating children and fostering positive learning experiences can inform the development of interventions and support mechanisms for parents in modular learning settings.

Furthermore, the third theme highlighted the Integrating Technologies and Online Resources as one of the coping strategies of parents. From the IDI, and observations participants shared the same strategies to rely on technologies and online resources to accomplish their child’s module. The result attested that it was a useful strategy for parents, especially if they were assisting with difficult and unfamiliar topics in MAPEH 5. It provided additional explanations and examples that can aid the child’s understanding towards the module. Participants shared:

“I google nalang gyud pero di man ta kabalo usahay sad aing internet na pasikot sikot ani.” (IDI P3)

“We’re just using Google, but we don’t know that much about how this internet works, it’s so complex.”

“Pina agi sa Google, mangutana sa maestra or manawag kay nay number or thru messenger.” (IDI P6)

“By using Google, ask the teacher through a phone call or messenger app.”

“Mao nang pag google ug unsay kapareha didto mao ra I answer di gud ko kabalo.” (IDI P10)

“When I see a similar answer while searching on Google.”

Observations:

The mother doesn’t want to dance because she doesn’t know how; she made the child follow only the dance on YouTube. (OF3)

The mother researched Notes topic on her cellphone. (OF5)

The father tried to do research on Google using his cell phone. (OM1)

In terms of integrating technologies and online resources, as one of the strategies of parents, this affirmed to the ecological systems theory of Bronfenbrenner (1979) which emphasizes the influence of the broader environment on a child's development. By accessing various online resources, parents expand the microsystem of the home environment to include digital platforms, enriching the learning experience within the mesosystem. This demonstrates the adaptation of parental strategies within the evolving technological landscape.

Moreover, the study by UNESCO Beirut (2020) recommended maintaining open communication channels, engaging with teachers and peers, and employing diverse learning methods for optimal educational outcomes. This finding resonates with the integration of technology and online resources, as parents actively engage in encouraging positive opinions and feelings toward education through digital platforms. By engaging in internet browsing for learning and seeking guidance from teachers online, parents actively participate in creating a supportive learning environment conducive to positive learning outcomes.

As for the fourth theme, Creating a Supportive Environment was also seen by parents as an effective coping strategy for their struggles. It showed that creating a supportive environment for children was essential not just for the accomplishment of their module but also for the parents to motivate and encourage their children. Participants employ that working together with the family members was also a best strategy to go through their struggles in assisting the modules. Participants shared:

“Pero actually ang coping bitaw nako, ako nalang siyang tabangan kanang mangutan ko unsa iyang kulang kay akoa nalang tan awon unsa akong matabang. Ing ana gyud ang mama. Pero ingon nga ako mu answer kay mag salig jud ang bata.” (IDI P3)

“I just can’t understand that they have been given quite enough time to do it but they really find it a habit to cram their outputs. But going back to the fact that I am their mom, I cope by helping them just so everything gets done.”

“Mag tinabanga mi sa akong bana. Kami duha mag tudlo unya murag usahay malipay na sad ko kay nahimo namo siyang bonding so di ra kaayo ko kapoyan kay malipay nalang sad ko mag tan aw.” (IDI P2)

“We work hand-in-hand with my husband. Sometimes, I even find myself happy as it seemed to have been something that drew us closer, something that bond us. Those were happy moments for me.”

Furthermore, in terms of creating a supportive environment, as one of the strategies of parents in coping with the difficulties they encounter in assisting their children with modular learning, this affirmed to the theory of Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (1979). Bronfenbrenner posits that a child's development is intricately influenced by various environmental systems, including the family, community, and broader societal contexts. Within this framework, parents play a crucial role as facilitators of their children's learning experiences, shaping the immediate environment where learning takes place.

Additionally, the study unveiled Grade 5 parents' deliberate focus on establishing such an environment amidst the challenges of Modular Learning, highlighting their commitment to cultivating a space conducive to effective learning. This intentional response underscored the acknowledgment of the crucial impact the learning environment has in shaping their children's educational journey (UNESCO Beirut,2020). By actively encouraging and motivating their children to engage with their modules, parents create a supportive learning environment conducive to academic success.

On the other hand, Table 3 presents the themes derived from the insights of Grade 5 parents regarding MAPEH modular learning which are—not effective for their children, disadvantage for the financially struggling families, and extra baggage for the intellectually challenged parents. It also highlighted the core ideas that encapsulate parents' perspectives on this educational approach.

Table 3. *Themes extracted from the insights of parents about modular learning*

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Subthemes</i>
Not Effective for their Children	Disassociation and Laziness
Disadvantage for the Financially Struggling Families	Uncertainty about Acquired Knowledge
	Financial Hardship Impacting Access
Extra Baggage for the Intellectually Challenged Parents	Limited Time for Parental Involvement
	Limitations in Knowledge as a Concern
	Proficiency Gaps in Educational Matters

On the other side, the first theme highlighted the insights of parents that modular learning is Not Effective for Children. They shared common experiences that children were not learning and become lazy on tasks that they need to accomplish. Parents also shared that they were anxious of the learning progress of their children. Participants shared:

“Wala gyud ang modular murag wala juy nakat unan.” (IDI P1)

“It was a hopeless case.”

“Dili gyud mayo ayy kay mag answer sila ug module answer nalang diretso wala nay basa basa.” (IDI P5)

“It's really not good because kids tend to answer their modules without reading the texts.”

“Dili gyud ko sure sa ilang learning gyud, bati gyud kaayo siya oyy kay usahay mangopya ra gyud tawon sila usahay mag salig ra sa answer key.” (IDI P4)

“I really am in doubt with the quality of learning that my kids get from this type of learning as it just normalizes cheating in exams. Most of the time, kids also depend on the answer key so I doubt where is the learning in that.”

Observations:

They finished the module without the child’s understanding. (OF3)

They did not finish the module because the child wasn’t listening. (OF4)

Moreover, the result not being effective for their children, as one of the insights of parents, underscores the complexities and challenges embedded within modular learning, affirming the theories of Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler (Afolabi, 2014; Reed et al., 2000). According to Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler's model, parents' motivations and beliefs significantly influence their involvement in their children's education (Walker et al., 2005). However, the findings reveal a disconnect between parental efforts and desired outcomes, indicating a discrepancy in parental expectations and the actual effectiveness of modular learning. The parents were acknowledged as pivotal contributors to their children's education, encountering a perplexing theme which was modular learning as ineffective.

Despite their integral role, doubts emerged about the efficacy of modular learning, revealing a gap between parental expectations and the perceived effectiveness of the educational model. Anzaldo (2021) discusses how functionally illiterate parents may have difficulty teaching their children, impacting modular distance learning. These findings underscore the necessity for comprehensive interventions and support mechanisms that address not only the academic challenges but also the socio-emotional and cognitive needs of both parents and children in modular learning settings.

Furthermore, the second theme was the Disadvantage of Modular Learning for Financially Struggling Families. The result showed from the extracted themes that most of the parents were minimum wage earners and deal with financial struggles, so they had to prioritize their livelihood rather than assisting their children in their module especially in the middle of the pandemic.

“Di gyud siya maayo para sa among mga kabos kay ug kanang mga ginikanan na gradahon ug nay mga human mas mayo gyud to unya sila ra mangunay ug tudlo.” (IDI P6)

“It’s very unfortunate for us parents who live in poverty because we’re obviously deprived of resources unlike the rich families where they surely have everything they need to cope with the changes.”

“Kay wa man koy hanaw ug usa pa di lang man kay module lang sa atong anak atong ge atubang naa man sad tay panginabuhian.” (IDI P9)

“It’s because I don’t have the enough knowledge and it’s also not just their modules that we must think about. We also need to prioritize our livelihood.”

“Kanang gyud ning busy kaayo ka kay trabaho di gyud nimo maatiman kay trabaho.” (IDI P10)

“It is when you can’t take care of it since you’re busy with your work.”

Subsequently, in terms of the disadvantage for financially struggling families, as one of the insights of parents, it becomes evident that economic hardship significantly impacts access to educational resources and parental involvement in modular learning. This observation resonates with the ecological systems theory of Bronfenbrenner (1979), which emphasizes the influence of broader environmental factors, including economic conditions, on child development and parental engagement.

Additionally, this theme unveiled a spectrum of struggles, encompassing emotional, cognitive, and socio-economic challenges as parents navigated the complexities of supporting their children within the modular learning framework. The study accentuated the need for targeted interventions, addressing issues of accessibility, tailored support, and the broader societal impact on the educational journey of intellectually challenged families (Ogurlu et al., 2020; Lase et al., 2020).

Another, the third theme was that modular learning is an added Baggage for the Intellectually Challenged Parents. The participants shared that it was an additional challenge for them because they must understand and navigate the modules prior to assisting their children, especially if they have limited educational backgrounds. Additionally, it was challenging for parents because they were not familiar with the teaching methods or the subject itself.

“Di gyud kay sa ka alam pa lang daan namong mga ginikanan di gyud namo mahatag sa among mga anak.” (IDI P9)

“I really don’t like it because considering our limitations in knowledge as parents, we really cannot fully help our children with it. We can only do so much.”

“Nag worry gyud ko kay kuan man usahay muingon ko answeri ra diha oyyy kung unsa imong nasabtan mao nang makaingon sad ko na sakto ba gyud kaha to iyahang ge answer.” (IDI P4)

“It worries me a lot as I often tend to instruct my son to just answer the modules based on whatever he understands as there’s really not much choices that we have.”

“Nabalaka jud ko oyy kay kanang di man ganahan kanang muingon nga ma oyy lisod man ni kay wala man kasabot mao ng naa ba kaha ni natun an.” (IDI P5)

“It gets me very worried especially when my kids tell me that they’re having a hard time understanding their lessons or that they’re not really learning at all.”

Observations:

The mother’s reading cannot be understood clearly. The mother reads slowly. (OF3)

You can see that the father doesn’t have enough knowledge of the subject because he just read it and let the child repeat. (OM2)

The father did not know what to do, and you can see that he is worried because his child did not learn anything. (OM3)

Interestingly, the result baggage for the intellectually challenged parents, as one of the insights of parents about modular learning, affirms Piaget’s Cognitive Development Theory which highlights the importance of social interaction, particularly with parents, in children’s cognitive development (Tekin, 2011). The struggles observed among intellectually challenged parents further underscore the significance of parental involvement in facilitating their children’s learning process, despite their own limitations in understanding the educational content.

In connection to this, this theme unveiled a spectrum of struggles, encompassing emotional, cognitive, and socio-economic challenges as parents navigated the complexities of supporting their children within the modular learning framework. The study accentuated the

need for targeted interventions, addressing issues of accessibility, tailored support, and the broader societal impact on the educational journey of intellectually challenged families (Ogurlu et al., 2020).

Conclusions

Parents have faced the demanding and time-consuming task of adapting to the sudden shift to a new educational approach. Balancing multiple responsibilities while ensuring their child's learning at the same time is a challenging task. It draws several struggles, experiences, emotions, and realizations from parents that modular learning is not effective for parents as well as for children. It added a burden to them not just physically but also emotionally and mentally. Despite the difficulties, parents faced their struggles by discovering common strategies, coping mechanisms and insights that significantly helped them during modular learning.

Implication for Practice

The study underscores the need for targeted training programs to enhance Grade 5 parents' knowledge of Modular Learning and practical strategies for time management, patience, and technology use. Simultaneously, ongoing module enhancements should address parents' concerns, providing guidance on balancing responsibilities, managing limited patience, and fostering a positive learning environment. This integrated approach aims to empower parents and optimize the effectiveness of Modular Learning for their children.

Implication for Future Research

The study suggests that researchers in the Department of Education, especially in MAPEH, should create specific training and module improvements for Grade 5 parents in Modular Learning. This involves developing strategies for time management, patience, and technology use, aligning MAPEH modules with parental concerns for an optimal learning environment. Additionally, researchers may explore academic performance, long-term skill retention, and teaching styles of parents in MAPEH subjects during modular learning.

Finally, as a researcher, I learned that this study proves that parents are not ready to adapt the new approach of learning due to the incapacity with regards to their capability, intelligence, and finances that could greatly affect the learning progress of their children. The study sheds light on the intricate challenges faced by Grade 5 parents in the context of Modular Learning, particularly within the MAPEH subject area. The findings underscore the critical need for targeted training programs and module enhancements that address specific concerns such as time management, patience, and technology use. This focused approach aims to empower parents and optimize the effectiveness of MAPEH education. As a researcher within the Department of Education, these insights highlight the importance of continually adapting educational strategies to meet the evolving needs of parents and students in the modular learning environment. Personally, this study underscores the dynamic interplay between parental engagement and effective education delivery, emphasizing the pivotal role of educators and researchers in creating a supportive and enriching learning experience for both parents and students in the ever-changing educational landscape.

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